

Concurrent metocean data analysis for holistic marine energy design and resource assessments

Abstract

Metocean environmental conditions, including waves, wind, and current, were usually investigated individually for their corresponding assessments of marine energy resources and types of marine energy devices (wave energy converter, offshore wind turbine, and ocean current turbine, respectively). However, due to the co-location of marine energy resources, different types of marine energy devices can be deployed at the same site. In addition, a rigorous marine energy device design should consider all the environmental conditions acting on the device for both structural design and mooring design. In this paper, the concurrent wave, wind, and current conditions at the U.S. PacWave South ocean test site are investigated based on history measurements from buoys located nearby. The results include plots of concurrent wind conditions (speed and direction) and wave conditions (presented in a wave histogram), and concurrent current conditions and wave conditions. The metocean conditions are grouped in clusters. The presentative wave-wind-current condition of each cluster is provided for marine energy device design.